

**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**
[ISSN: 0975-4725; CODEN(USA): IJPS00]
Journal Homepage: <https://www.ijpsjournal.com>

Research Article

“Folate From Strawberries” A Sustainable Solution for Anemia, Prevention and Treatment

Mounika K.*, K. B. Ilango, Ajith M. S., Babu S., Kalpana D., Nishanth Kannan B., Ramya R., Selvakumar R.

Shree Venkateshwara College of Paramedical Sciences, College of Pharmacy, Erode, Tamilnadu, The Tamilnadu Dr. M. G. R. Medical University.

ARTICLE INFO

Published: 14 Feb. 2025

Keywords:

Strawberries, Folate, Folate Deficiency Anemia, Extraction delivery.

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.14870157

ABSTRACT

It is estimated that > 2 billion people globally are affected by the deficiency of ≥ 1 micronutrients. Micronutrient deficiency affects people of all age groups but children and women are the most vulnerable. Folic acid, also known as folate or Vitamin B9, is a member of the B vitamin family and it is a water-soluble vitamin an essential cofactor for enzymes involved in DNA and RNA synthesis. More specifically, folic acid is required by the body for the synthesis of purines, pyrimidines, and methionine before incorporation into DNA or protein. strawberry, (genus *Fragaria*), genus of more than 20 species of flowering plants in the rose family (Rosaceae) and it is an edible fruit. The strawberry (*Fragaria X ananassa*, Duch.) represents a relevant source of micronutrients, such as minerals, vitamin C, folate and phenolic substances, most of which are natural antioxidants and contribute to the high nutritional quality of the fruit. In this research article we extract the folate from strawberries for the folate deficiency prevention and treatment.

INTRODUCTION

Anemia is defined as a reduction in hemoglobin (Hb) concentration, Hematocrit, or a number of red blood cells per litter below the reference interval for healthy individuals of similar age, sex and race under similar environmental condition. According to, World Health Organization (WHO)

for under five years children, the threshold Hb level for being anemic is less than 11,0g/dl. It is a common clinical condition characterized by decreased Hb level which are insufficient for the body's demand. Anemia is a global public health problem which affects more than 2 million people (24.8%) people worldwide more prevalently it

***Corresponding Author:** Mounika K.

Address: Shree Venkateshwara College of Paramedical Sciences, College of Pharmacy, Erode, Tamilnadu, The Tamilnadu Dr. M. G. R. Medical University.

Email : mounika.mythu@gmail.com

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

affects mostly children and women. Folate deficiency anemia is a decreased in red blood cells (Anemia) due to lack of folate or when the body doesn't have enough Vitamin B9 or Folate/Vitamin B12, which prevents the bone marrow from producing healthy red blood cells. Without these nutrients, the red blood cells are unable to carry oxygen throughout the body and die prematurely. Folate is a type of vitamin B. It is also called folic acid. In this type of anemia, the red blood cells are abnormally large. They are also called megaloblasts, when they are seen in the bone marrow. That is why anemia is also called a type of Megaloblastic anemia. Strawberry was recognized as the best fruit ever produced in the world by early romans. The fruit represented the goddess of love – Venus due to its heart shaped and colour. Strawberry *Fragaria ananassa* is a

member of family *Rosaceae* and genus *Fragaria*. It is originated in the 18th century. Botanically, strawberry is not a berry and grows on perennial woody plant. Strawberry is a herbaceous evergreen shrub that grows along the ground and it consists of fibrous rod system and a crown from which basal leaves arise. The strawberry (*Fragaria ananassa*, Duch.) represents the relevant source of micronutrients such as, minerals, vitamin C, Folate and phenolic substances most of the which are natural antioxidants and contribute to high nutritional quality of the fruit. All these compounds are essential for health. In this research we extract the folate from the strawberries and gives the information about the folate for the Folate deficiency anemia.

Drug Profile

Figure 1

Folate

Introduction

Folate or Folic acid is an N-acyl-amino acid that is a form of the water-soluble vitamin B9. It is the member of the B vitamin family. Its biologically active forms (tetrahydrofolate and others) are essential for nucleotide biosynthesis and homocysteine remethylation. It has a role as a human metabolite, a nutrient and a mouse metabolite. It is a member of folic acids and a N-acyl-amino acid. It is functionally related to a

pterotic acid. It is an essential cofactor for enzymes involved in DNA and RNA synthesis. More specifically, folic acid is required by the body for the synthesis of purines, pyrimidines, and methionine before incorporation into DNA or protein. Folic acid is particularly important during phases of rapid cell division, such as infancy, pregnancy, and erythropoiesis, and plays a protective factor in the development of cancer. As humans are unable to synthesize folic acid endogenously, diet and supplementation is

necessary to prevent deficiencies. Folic acid is present in liver, kidney and is found in mushroom, spinach, green leaves & vegetables, avocado, and some citrus fruits. Inadequate folate levels can result in a number of health concerns including cardiovascular disease, megaloblastic anemias, cognitive deficiencies, and neural tube defects (NTDs). Folic acid is typically supplemented during pregnancy to prevent the development of NTDs and in individuals with alcoholism to prevent the development of neurological disorders. A member of Vitamin B family stimulates the hematopoietic system. Folic acid is used in the treatment and prevention of folate deficiencies and megaloblastic anemia.

Synonyms

The synonyms of Vitamin B9 is Folate, Folic acid, 59-30-3, Pteroylglutamic acid, Vitamin M

Molecular Formula

Molecular formula of folate is **C₁₉H₁₉N₇O₆**.

Molecular Weight

Molecular weight of folate is 441.4g/mol.

Physical Properties

It appears as odorless orange-yellow platelets or needles (yellowish-orange solid). Darkens and chars from approximately 482°F

Colour/Form

Yellowish-Orange

Odour

Odourless

Taste

Tasteless

Solubility

It is almost insoluble. Slightly soluble in methanol and less in ethanol and butanol. Insoluble in benzene, ether, chloroform, acetone. Relatively soluble in acetic acid, phenol, pyridine. Soluble in hot dil.HCL and H₂SO₄. In water 1.6mg/l at 25°C. Soluble up to 1% in boiling water.

Melting Point

Melting point of folate is 482°F.

Shelf Life/Stability

Aqueous solution of folic acid are heat sensitive and decomposes rapidly in the presence of riboflavin or light. Solution should be protected from light.

Drugs

Human Drugs

Paediatric drugs, Antianemia medicines.

Cosmetics

Skin conditioning.

Food Additives

Nutrient supplement.

Pesticides

Plant growth regulators.

Therapeutic Uses

Haematinics: Folic acid is indicated for the treatment of folic acid deficiency, megaloblastic anemia and in anemias of nutritional origins, pregnancy, infancy or childhood.

Absorption, Distribution and Excretion

Absorption

Folic acid is absorbed rapidly from the small intestine, primarily from the proximal portion. Naturally occurring conjugated folates are reduced enzymatically to folic acid in the gastrointestinal tract in prior to absorption. Folic acid appears in the plasma approximately 15 to 30 minutes after an oral dose, peak levels are generally reached within 1 hour.

Volume Of Distribution

Tetrahydrofolic acid derivatives are distributed to all body tissues but are stored primarily in liver.

Route Of Elimination

After a single dose of 100mcg folic acid in a limited number of normal adults. Only a trace amount of drug appeared in the urine. An oral dose of 5mg in 1 study and dose of 40mcg/kg of body weight in another study resulted in approximately 50% of the dose appearing in the urine. After a single oral dose of 15mcg, up to 90% of the dose was recovered in the urine. A majority of the metabolic products appeared in the urine after 6

hours, excretion was generally complete within 24 hours. Small amounts of orally administered folic acid have also been recovered in feces. Folic acid is also excreted in the milk of lactating mothers.

Metabolism

Folic acid is metabolised in the liver into the cofactors dihydrofolate (DHF) and Tetrahydrofolate (THF) by the enzyme dihydrofolate reductase (DHFR).

Mechanism Of Action

Folic acid is biochemically inactive, is converted to tetrahydrofolic acid and methyl tetrahydrofolate reductase (DHFR). These folic acid congeners are transported across cell by receptor mediated endocytosis where they are needed to maintain normal erythropoiesis, synthesize purine and thymidylate nucleic acids, interconvert amino acids, methylate Trna and generate and use formate. Using vitamin B12 as a cofactor, folic acid can normalize high homocysteine levels by remethylation of homocysteine to methionine via methionine synthetase.

Hazards

Health Hazards

Symptoms of exposure to this compound include anorexia, nausea, abdominal distension, flatulence, altered sleep and dream patterns, malaise, irritability, hypersensitivity and fever. It may also cause allergic sensitization.

Acute/Chronic Hazards

When heated to decomposition this compound emits toxic fumes of NOx.

Fire Hazards

Flash point data for this chemical are not available. However, it is probably combustible.

Hazards Summary

Rare allergic reactions after IV injection reported may cause allergic sensitization, may cause irritation.

First Aid Measures:

Eyes

First check the victim for contact lenses and remove if present. Flush victim's eyes with water or normal saline solution for 20 to 30 minutes while simultaneously, calling a hospital or poison control center. Don't put any oils, ointment's or medications in the victim's eye without specific instructions from a physician. IMMEDIATELY transport the victim after flushing eyes to a hospital even if no symptoms such as redness or irritation develop.

Skin

Immediately flood affected skin with water while removing and isolating all contaminated clothing. Gently, wash all affected skin areas thoroughly with soap and water. If symptoms such as redness or irritation develops, IMMEDIATELY call a physician and be prepared to transport the victim to a hospital for treatment.

Inhalation

Immediately leave the contaminated area; take deep breaths of fresh air. If symptoms (such as wheezing, coughing, shortness of breath or burning in the mouth, throat or chest) develop call a physician and be prepared to transport the victim to a hospital. Provide proper respiratory protection to rescuers entering an unknown atmosphere. Whenever possible, Self-Contained Breathing Apparatus (SCBA) should be used. If not available, use a level of protection greater than or equal to that advised under protective clothing.

Ingestion

Do Not Induce Vomiting. If the victim is conscious and not convulsing, give 1 or 2 glasses of water to dilute the chemical and IMMEDIATELY call a hospital or poison control center. Be prepared to transport the victim to a hospital if advised by a physician. If the victim is convulsing or unconscious, do not give anything by mouth ensure that the victim is open and lay the victim on his/her side with the head lower than the body. Do Not Induce Vomiting. Immediately transport the victim to a hospital.

Fire Fighting

Fires involving this material can be controlled with a dry chemical carbon dioxide or Halon extinguisher.

Disposal Methods

The most favourable course of action is to use an alternative chemical product with less inherent propensity for occupational exposure or environmental contamination. Recycle and unused portion for the material for its approved use or return it to the manufacture or supplier. Ultimate disposal of the chemical must consider. The materials impact on air quality, potential migration in soil or water, effects on animal, aquatic and plant life and conformance with environmental and public health regulations.

Storage Conditions

Store below 40°C (104°F), preferably between 15 and 30°C (59 to 86°F), unless otherwise specified by manufacturer. Protect from freezing.

Folate For Health

Folate and folic acid are used in supplements. Although these two nutrients treat the same conditions, they are metabolized differently in the body and can affect health in different ways.

The common uses and benefits of folic acid supplements.

Treating Folate Deficiency

Folate deficiency can happen for many reasons. Some possible cause of folate deficiency are:

- A lack of folate in diet
- Diseases or surgeries that affect how your body absorbs folate, including celiac disease, short bowel syndrome and gastric bypass surgery.
- No stomach acid(achlorhydria) or low stomach acid (Hypochlorhydria).
- Drugs that affect folate absorption including methotrexate and sulfasalazine (Azulfadine).
- Alcohol use disorder
- Hemolytic anemia
- Dialysis

Consuming too little folate can cause complications such as anemia, fetal development issues, mental impairment, impaired immune function and depression. Taking folic acid or folate supplement can bring your levels and prevent these complications.

Preventing Birth Defects and Pregnancy Complications

Folic acid supplements can help to prevent neural tube irregularities including spina bifida and anencephaly. Getting enough folic acid during pregnancy can reduce the chance that your body will be born with one of these conditions. Folic acid supplements not only help prevent fetal development issues but also help lower the risk of pregnancy complications such as preeclampsia.

Maintaining Brain Health

Low blood folate levels are linked to poor mental function and an increased risk of dementia. Even folate levels that are technically normal but on the low side might increases the risk of mental impairment in older adults. Adequate folate intake may also help to protect against Alzheimer's disease. In 2019 study in adults with mild cognitive impairment, taking 400mcg of folic acid supplements daily for 2 years improved measures of brain function and reduced blood levels of proteins that are involved in Alzheimer's disease. Another study looked at 121 people with newly diagnosed Alzheimer's disease who were being treating with the medications donepezil (Aricept).

Those who also took 1250 mcg of folic acid per day for 6months had improved thinking ability and less inflammation than those who took Aricept alone.

Treating Mental Conditions

Folate is involved in the production of brain chemicals called neurotransmitters. Consuming too little folate has been linked to depression, schizophrenia and other mental health conditions. For example, people with depression may have lower blood levels of folate than people without

depression. A 2022 review of studies suggests that folic acid and folate supplements may help reduce symptoms of mental health conditions such as postpartum depression, schizophrenia and bipolar disorder. Taking folate supplements in addition to antidepressant medication may reduce depression symptoms more than taking antidepressant medication alone. A review of seven studies found that treatment with folate supplements plus antipsychotic medication may improve symptoms in people with schizophrenia more than antipsychotic medication alone. However, larger, more robust studies are needed to further support these findings.

Reducing Heart Disease Risk Factors

Folate based supplements including folic acid may help improve heart health and reduce the risk of heart disease. High levels of the amino acid homocysteine are thought to increase heart risk. Because, folate helps break down homocysteine low folate can lead to high homocysteine levels also known as hyperhomocysteinemia. Folic acid supplements can help bring down homocysteine levels and may lower heart disease risk. For example, a review that included 30 studies with more than 80000 total participant's showed that supplementing with folic acid led to a 4% reduction in overall heart disease risk and a 10% reduction in stroke risk. Using folic acid supplements along with anti-hypertensive medications may reduce blood pressure significantly more than anti-hypertensive medications alone. Folic acid supplements may also improve blood vessel function in people with heart disease.

Other Possible Benefits of Folate Diabetes

Folate supplements may help improved blood sugar regulation and reduce insulin resistance in people with diabetes. Because, the diabetes drug metformin can lower folate levels you may need a supplement if your levels are low.

Fertility Issues

Folate supplements can improve egg quality and help eggs grow and implant in the uterus. Taking folate may increase the chance of getting pregnant and carrying a baby to term. People who use assisted reproductive technology to conceive may be more likely to have a baby if they have a higher intake of supplemental folate.

Inflammation

Inflammation plays a role in many diseases. Folic acid and folate supplements have been shown to reduce markers of inflammation such as C-reactive protein.

Kidney Disease

The kidneys filter waste out of blood. When the kidney are damaged, homocysteine can build up. About 85% of people with chronic kidney disease have too much homocysteine levels and heart disease risk in people with kidney disease.

Folate Deficiency Anemia

Folate deficiency Anemia

It is estimated that > 2 billion people were globally affected by the deficiency of ≥ 1 micronutrients. Unlike protein energy malnutrition, the consequences of micronutrient deficiency, also known as "Hidden Hunger", are typically not visible but manifest as impaired physical and mental health, weakened immune systems and exacerbated infections and decreased productivity. Micronutrient deficiency affects people of all age groups but children and women are the most vulnerable. The nutritional status of a woman not only influences her health but also is determinant of fetal growth and development, with subsequent impacts throughout the child's life course. Adults need 200 micrograms of folate and the pregnant woman is recommended to take 400 micrograms of folic acid supplement daily until 12 weeks pregnant. It is need to take folic acid supplement before pregnant. This is to help prevent Neural Tube Defects, such as spina bifida in baby. If she has NTD they are advised to take a higher dose of 5mg of folic acid each day until they are 12 weeks

pregnant. A microgram is 1000 times smaller than a milligram(mg). It is sometimes written with the Greek symbol μ followed by the letter g (μg). There are no longer term stories in the body, so you need to eat folate containing foods frequently. Most people should be able to get the amount of folate they need by eating a varied and balanced diet. Folate-deficiency anemia is the lack of folic acid in the blood. Folic acid is a B vitamin that helps your body make a red blood cells. If you don't have enough red blood cells, you have anemia. Red blood cells carry oxygen to all parts of your body. When you have anemia, your blood can't bring enough oxygen to all your tissues and organs Without enough oxygen, your body cannot work as well as it should Folate deficiency anemia can also lead to megaloblastic anemia in adults and children through impaired DNA synthesis and cell division leading to ineffective erythropoiesis. With this condition, red blood cells are larger than normal. There are fewer of these cells. They also oval-shaped, not round. Sometimes, these red blood cells don't live long as normal red blood cells. Maternal anemia and NTD – defected pregnancies are among most important health outcomes of folate deficiency. Folate deficiency has been linked with incidence of chronic diseases such as cardiovascular disease, cancer and the progression of cognitive impairment in older people.

Pathophysiology

Folate is present in green leafy vegetables, citrus fruits, and animal products. Folate is poorly stored, and deficiency can develop in weeks to months in persons with folate-deficient diets. Most of the serum folate is present in the inactive 5-methyltetrahydrofolate (5-methyl THFA) form. Upon entering cells, 5-methyl THFA demethylates to THFA, the biologically active form involved in folate-dependent enzymatic reactions. Cobalamin (B-12) serves as a co-factor for this demethylation to occur, and in its absence, folate is "trapped"

inside cells as 5-methyl THFA. THFA is involved in the formation of many coenzymes in metabolic systems, particularly for purine and pyrimidine synthesis, nucleoprotein synthesis, and maintenance in erythropoiesis. The deficiency of folate, as a result, leads to impairment of cell division, accumulation of toxic metabolites, and impairment of methylation reactions required for regulation of gene expression.

The body has about 1,000-20,000 mcg of folate stores, and adults need about 400 mcg/d to replenish the daily losses. Folate deficiency may take 8 to 16 weeks to become evident.

Causes

Folate deficiency anemia can develop if:

- You don't eat enough foods that have folic acid. These include leafy vegetables, fresh vegetables, Fresh fruits Fortified cereals, yeast and meats (including liver).
- You drink too much alcohol.
- You have certain diseases of the lower digestive tract, such as celiac disease. This type of anemia also occurs in people with cancer.
- You take certain medicines such as some used for seizures.
- You are pregnant. This is because the developing baby needs more folic acid. Also, the mother absorbs it more slowly. A lack of folate during pregnancy is linked with major birth defects that affect the brain, spinal cord and spine (Neural Tube Defects).

Symptoms

- Pale skin
- Decreased appetite
- Being grouchy (irritable)
- Lack of energy or tiring easily
- Diarrhea
- Smooth and tender tongue

The symptoms of folate deficiency anemia may look like other like other blood conditions or health problems.

Complications

Untreated folic acid deficiency can lead to megaloblastic anemia and pancytopenia. In addition, it can cause, glossitis, angular stomatitis and oral ulcers. Neuropsychiatric manifestations including depression, irritability, insomnia, cognitive decline, fatigue and psychosis also occur with folic acid deficiency.

Diagnosis And Examinations

A medical professional will physically and go over your symptoms and medical history. In order to get a definitive diagnosis, doctors perform blood tests because the symptoms of folate deficiency anemia might be confused with those of many other illnesses.

Lab examinations could consist of:

➤ Complete Blood Count (CBC)

The complete blood count (CBC) measures the quantity of hemoglobin in your body as well as the quantity of red, white and platelet blood.

➤ Peripheral Blood Smear (PBS)

Under a microscope, a peripheral blood smear (PBS) displays the size and form of your blood cells.

➤ Reticulocyte Count

Assesses your bone marrow's supply of immature red blood cells or reticulocytes, to see if you are making enough of them.

Additionally, your healthcare professional will measure the folate levels in your blood and compare them with this scale;

- Less than 2 nanograms per milliliter (ng/mL) is considered deficient.
- In the range of 2 and 4 (ng/mL) is the borderline.

- Adequate: Exceeding (4ng/mL).

Treatment

The best treatment should be figure out Based on,

- Your age, overall health, medical history
- How sick you are
- How well you can handle certain medicines, treatment or therapies.
- How long the condition expected to last?
- **Your Opinion or Preference**

All patients with folate deficiency should be offered supplemental folic acid for the correction of the folate deficiency. Typically, oral folic acid (1 to 5mg daily) sufficient to treat folate acid deficiency. Intravenous, subcutaneous or intramuscular formulations of folic acid can be used in patients unable to tolerate oral medications. Folinic acid (also called leucovorin), a reduced form of folate is primarily the initial deficiency persists. Patients with malabsorption or short gut syndromes may typically require long-term treatment. You need to take folic acid supplements for 2 to 3 months. If a digestive problem may cause anemia your provider should treat that first. Diet changes can help boost your folate level. Eat more green, leafy vegetables and citrus fruits.

Preventions

Eat plenty of folate rich foods can help prevent this condition. Experts recommended that woman take 400 to 800 micrograms (mcg) of folic acid everyday before they get pregnant and through the 1st three months of their pregnancy.

Figure 2
Strawberry

Plant Profile

Figure 3

Botanical Classification

Kingdom	Plantae
Division	Magnoliophyta
Class	Magnoliopsida
Order	Rosales
Family	Rosaceae
Genus	<i>Fragaria</i>
Species	<i>Ananasa</i>
Botanical name	<i>Fragaria ananasa</i>

The strawberry- *Fragaria ananassa*, belongs to the genus *Fragaria*, and is a member of the rose family, Rosaceae. The *ananassa* designation is due

to the resemblance to the pineapple in flavor, odor and shape. Strawberry plants are classified as a forb or herb. By the 18th century, *Fragaria vesca* began to replace by *Fragaria × ananassa*, the Garden Strawberry. This transition occurs because of the desirable traits exhibited by the newly bred strawberry plant, larger fruit and greater variation (easier to breed). The first strawberry hybrid, “Hudson”, was developed later (1780) in the United States.

Anatomy Of Strawberry Plant

Figure 4

In strawberry there are Five basic anatomical structures that make up a strawberry plant being. They are the leaf, root system, crown, stolon (more commonly called a ‘runner’), daughter strawberry plant, flower and fruit. The leaves are compound, typically with three leaflets, saw tooth-edged and usually hairy. The root of a strawberry plants with a fibrous root system which engages in photosynthesis or absorb nutrients and water from the soil in order to facilitate growth and reproduction. As a plant ages, the root system becomes woody. As the top three inches of soil contain about 70% of a strawberry plants roots, they are particularly susceptible to drought conditions. The productive engine of the strawberry plant is contained within the crown. It is from this region that strawberry plants produce both runners (stolons) and flowering fruit stalks that eventually yield strawberries. Containing the growth energy of a plant by clipping runners and early flower buds can cause crown multiplication, which will often result in more, higher – quality fruit per plant in subsequent years. The daughter plants are maintained by the runners until their root bud comes into contact with soil and establishes an independent root system. At that point, the runner will dry, shrivel and eventually separate completely leaving a new and independent

strawberry plant clone. The flowers of strawberries are generally, white, rarely reddish are borne in small clusters on slender stalks arising like the surface creeping stems from the axils of the leaves. The principal parts of the flower receptacle, pistil and fruit wall, anther, sepal and petal. The strawberry flower has 5 sepals. The stamens are the male parts of the flower that discharge pollen to fertilize the ‘female’ parts of the flower called pistils. The numerous pistils are borne on a roundish or conic shaped flower supporting stem called the ‘receptacle’. At maturity, the receptacle becomes the enlarged, juicy ‘Berry’. Botanically, the red fruit we call the ‘Berry’ is an enlarged flower stem (receptacle) with many seeds imbedded in the surface. Actually, what looks like seeds really are the ‘true fruits’ properly referred to as achenes. Inside the dry ovary wall of each achene is a real seed (ovule) with the potential of becoming a unique strawberry plant (seedling). This offspring is not likely to have any of the desirable horticultural characteristics of the parent strawberry. To preserve strawberry varieties which yield superior fruit, strawberry propagation is generally accomplished by taking runner plants that are identical genetic make up to the ‘mother plant’.

Fruit cluster. Primary berries are not only the largest and first to ripen they have the most seeds. Secondary berries ripen next are the next largest in size. Tertiary berries ripen still later and are the third largest. Quaternary berries are the smallest and ripen last. Development of the fruit from open blossom to ripeness take 20 to 30 days, depending on weather conditions. The fruit is 5–10 cm in length, 2–3 cm broad with serrated margins. Strawberry fruit is bright red in colour and is heart shaped with rough surface and 1–2 cm in diameter. Strawberry is not a true berry and is known as accessory fruit.

Chemical Constituents

The unique combinations of nutrients, phytochemicals and fiber found in strawberries appears to work synergistically to provide several health benefits. The polyphenols and vitamins in strawberries are considered to be the components primarily responsible for their antioxidant and anti-inflammatory activities, with a single serving providing more than 1mg of polyphenols. Bioavailability of polyphenols has been shown to be low in *in vivo*. Kaemferol, quercetin glycosides, cyaniding, pelargonin, ellagic acid and ellagittins are among the approximately 40 different phenolic compounds that have been identified. Strawberries ranked second soluble phenolic content among nopal, papaya, guava, black sapote, avocado, mango and prickly pear. Strawberries are an important source of vitamins C (60 mg per 100 g of fresh fruit) and E, B Vitamins, Folate (24mcg per 100g of fresh fruit), carotenoids, potassium and phytosterols as well as the flavonoids pelargonidin, quercetin and catechin. Other nutritional phytochemicals include vitamin A, vitamin K, manganese, iodine, magnesium, copper, iron and phosphorous as well as dietary fiber and fructose. Glucose, fructose and sucrose are the major soluble sugars found in the fruit with glucose and fructose found in almost equal

concentrations, these 3 sugars are found during all stages of ripening.

Carbohydrates

Fresh strawberries are high in water which means that the fruit is a low source weight. Most of the carbohydrates is in the form of simple sugars—glucose, fructose and sucrose with fructose being the predominant. The total sugar content of fruit is 4.89 g/1Wg. The net digestive carbohydrate content of fruit is less than 6 g for every 100 g and the GI source is 40 which are selectively low.

Protein

Strawberries contain a meagre amount of protein 10.67 g/100 g and are also devoid of some essential amino acids like methionine. Moreover, the protein quality of accessory fruit is poor. Amino acids like cysteine, tryptophan and isoleucine are present as traces. However, glutamic acid is relatively a predominant amino acid in strawberries.

Fiber

The fibre content of fruit is around 2 g/1 g which account for 26% of the total carbohydrate content. The fibre from strawberries has a daily value (DV) of 10%.

The ratio of soluble to insoluble fibre is 0.28.

Lipids

Strawberry fruit is a low fat food with a total fat content of 0.29 g. Moreover, the little fat present is in the form of polyunsaturated DV (%). The predominant fatty acid in strawberries is linoleic acid (omega-6) with a DV of 4%.

Minerals

The total mineral content of fruit is 0.49 g/1Wg. Like other fruits, strawberries are a rich source of potassium, phosphorous, magnesium, calcium and chloride. Besides these, the fruit also contains selenium, boron and iodine. Despite manganese element being present in limited amount in strawberry, its DV is highest (24).

Vitamins

Strawberries are an abundant source of vitamin C. The ascorbic acid content of fruit is approx. 84.67 mg/100 g with the highest DV (113%) among all the micro as well as macro nutrients. Besides these, other water-soluble vitamins like choline, folate are also provided by strawberries. Furthermore, strawberries are relatively a poor source of fat-soluble vitamins and contain vitamin K and E in insignificant amounts. Strawberry is the dense source of important vitamin folate, an important element in maintaining health and treatment of ailments.

Organic Acids

The major organic acid in strawberry is citric acid (420 mg/100 g) followed by malic (90 mg/100 g) and ascorbic acid (26 mg/100 g). Other organic acids such as tartaric, succinic and pyruvic acid are also present in least amounts. Organic acids

contribute to the characteristic taste and tartness of the fruit.

Phytonutrients

More than 25 anthocyanidins are present in strawberries. Pelargonidin, the main anthocyanin in strawberry is responsible for its colour. Ellagitannins and ellagic acid is found in high amounts in strawberries. Pelargonidin and procyanidins are the main anthocyanins in strawberry. Strawberries are ranked as top sources of phenolics and have 2–10 times higher phenolic content than other fruits. Ellagitannins are the second most abundant class of phytochemicals in strawberries. The main ellagitannin in strawberries is sanjin, followed by flavonols (i.e. quercetin and kaempferol-3-malonylglucoside), flavanols (i.e. catechins and procyanidins) and phenolic acids.

Strawberries- Nutritional Facts per 100 g

Nutrients mg Percentage

Folates	24 µg	6%
Niacin	0.386 mg	2.5%
Pantothenic acid	0.125 mg	2.5%
Pyridoxine	0.047 mg	3.5%
Riboflavin	0.022 mg	2%
Vitamin A	12 IU	0.5%
Vitamin C	58.8 mg	98%
Vitamin E	0.29 mg	2%
Vitamin K	2.2 µg	2%
Sodium	1 mg	0%
Potassium	153 mg	3%
Calcium	16 mg	1.6%
Iron	0.41 mg	5%
Magnesium	13 mg	3%
Manganese	0.386 mg	17%
Zinc	0.14 mg	1%

Figure 5

Pharmacological Activity

Nutritional Health Benefits of Strawberry

Anthocyanin are relative with an extensive health benefits including lower risk of Cardiovascular disease, less risk of cancer also protects brain tissue from hypoxic ischemic injury. Improved vision, memory and as well as suppression of putting on weight. Apoptosis induction is the major contribution of berry phenolics, especially anthocyanin's. These phenolic also have anti-microbial properties which help to manage the

natural spectra of pathogens against antibiotic resistance. The phenolic also possess anti-oxidant properties that contribute to protect humans from degenerative diseases and their effects on health. Phenolic may also cause toxicity because of their pro-oxidant activity, inducing properties, apoptosis and their relations with drug metabolizing enzymes action by making complexes with other elements that catalyze oxidation reactions.

Strawberry Ameliorate Lipid Profile and Lipid Oxidation In Females:

Epidemiological observations also imply that strawberries have valuable effects on cardiovascular activity of women. The women's health study revealed that strawberry intake has a significant inverse relation with cardiovascular disease mortality among 34489 obese postmenopausal women another study between 26966 obese postmenopausal women recommended that intake of strawberries two times a week reduces the chance of superior CRP. It was also observed that frozen strawberries consumption reduced serum cholesterol levels this study suggests a need for future studies to verify their beneficial role as possible nutritional approach that can lower cholesterol in chubby women. Phytosterols, potassium, fiber, vitamin C, folic acid and phytochemicals are known agents in strawberries that are cardio protective and contribute to the anti-inflammatory, anti-oxidant and hypo-cholesterolemic activities. Some non-conclusive results showed positive correlation between shelf life of strawberries anti-oxidant capacity and disease susceptibility. Phenolic compounds delays senescence of fresh fruit by inducing oxidative degradation and thus contribute to extend the shelf life and improved fruit quality.

Strawberry And Cholesterol Lowering Diet

Strawberries maintain serum lipid reduction of daily diet and can improve palatability of cholesterol lowering food. The risk of cardiovascular attack are reduced by inhibition of LDL cholesterol oxidation caused by antioxidants present in strawberries, it also promotes sign stability, decreased tendency of thrombosis, better vascular endothelial functions, suppresses regulation and proliferation of tumors and I also have anti-cancerous effects suggested that cholesterol level can be lowered by eating freeze dried strawberry powder may be responsible for cholesterol lowering. Clinical studies revealed that

the lower cholesterol levels and reduce cholesterol absorption is due to phytosterols. Cholesterol lowering effect can be due to dietary fiber present in strawberry reversing or slowing the process of atherosclerotic heart problems in over weight females with factors of metabolic risk that may be achieved by long term intake of anti-oxidant rich fruits example; strawberry. Strawberry powder supplementation enhances lipids and lipid peroxidation. Lipid peroxidation in females with metabolic disorder can be achieved by ingesting strawberry as a natural source of phytosterols, polyphenolic flavonoids and fiber present in FSP.

Anti-Cancerous Effect Of Strawberry Phytochemicals

The phenolic constituents of the berries through multi mechanistic mean of action including the anti-oxidation protects DNA from damage and also their effects are exerted outside thus leading to antic-cancerous affects. The lignans from plant origin adds to plasma and urinary intensity of mammalian entero lactone are present in ample amount as constituent of berries. The past auto-oxidation and multiple step mechanism action including anti-oxidant protection of DNA from oxidative damage is a result of strawberry phytochemicals which protects human from cancer. Viral parasitic infections and Chronic bacteria can be caused by over production of these anti-oxidants as an imbalance leads to oxidative stress that can cause oxidative damage to bigger biomolecules such as lipids, proteins and DNA resulting in an increased risk for cancer and heart disease. Apoptotic effects have been shown in human cancer cells by the berry extracts. There is a need to consume sufficient amount of anti-oxidants avoid or reduce the oxidative stress stimulated by free radicals. The risk of persistent disease and oxidative damage to the cellular system can be prohibited or lowered by anti-oxidant compounds such as, phenolics and carotenoids present in the natural fresh food. The

cell signaling pathways, the modulation of gene expression and the inhibition of transcription factors caused suppression of cancer cell proliferation, transformation and tumor progression this have been entailed as major contribution of strawberry phytochemicals. Fruits like strawberry contains dietary anti-oxidant prevent or limit the potential cancer-inducing oxidative damage. The anti-angiogenic and chemo preventive properties of the extracts have been recorded, due to their ability to inhibit mutagenesis caused by several carcinogens. Another mechanism of action of strawberry phenolics hypothesized by inhibitory effects of these compounds on enzymes implicated in cancer development, such as phase-II detoxification enzymes and cyclo oxygenase enzymes Cyclooxygenase enzymes, converts arachidonic acid to eicosanoids and is linked with the development of inflammation, is considered as part of common pathway of many chronic disease development hypothetically. The phenol mechanisms and unit of tissue distribution and accumulation after berry intake does not determine the direct effect of these compounds in the health benefits correlated with the whole fruit. Strawberries have great potential as chemo-preventative agents in that their naturally-occurring phytochemical compounds have health-promoting properties that can prevent disease progression, malignancy, and recurrence. demonstrated the anti-proliferative activity of strawberry extracts on human lung epithelial cancer cell lines. Strawberry extract was found to decrease the activity of transcription factors involved in tumour promotion mediators, specifically activator protein-1 (AP-1) and nuclear factor-KB (NF-KB), in TPA- or UVB-induced tumour promotion as well as inhibited MAPK signalling, reported a dose-dependent anti-proliferative effect in oral cell lines with a phenolic-enriched strawberry extract. Inhibition of

proliferation of humor oral tumor cell lines with both crude extracts and 32 isolated compounds from strawberries was reported. Similiarly, it was found that strawberry extract was able to stimulate apoptosis in human HT-29 colon cancer cell lines.

Strawberry Consumption and Urate Level

Nutritional quality of many fruits is now evaluated by using the antioxidant ability (TAC) of fruit extracts; it is also used as a measure of antioxidant concentration in the food matrix. The considerable raise in plasma or serum TAC is always linked with the consumption of flavonoid rich foods. As per observation of the consumption of different types of fruit without uric acid contributes to the increase of the serum concentrations of urate, which is a very important contribution to plasma antioxidant effect. However, recent studies hypothesized that fructose present in fruits like apples may possibly be responsible for the increase in plasma urate. Linneaus, further confirmed the role of strawberries as a gout reliever. Adding to it another herbalist message from France encouraged strawberry regime for persons suffering from kidney stones or gout. Many researchers conducted experiments to verify the serum level concentration before and after strawberry consumption, led to non-significant results due to the difference of the experimental designs and the analytical methods used. high concentration of vitamin C found in strawberry significantly increases the serum concentrations but no variation in the urate levels. However, experimental studies on people revealed that urate concentrations in response to strawberry consumption, ranging from slight modification to 50 % decrease and 20 %, it was measured that the serum urate up to 3 h of strawberries consumption had no change on urate level though it decreased later on; similar results were also observed for cherries.

Anti-Oxidant Activity of Strawberry

Recent studies have revealed that the phenolic compounds present in strawberries are responsible for antioxidant properties rather than to vitamin C. The Strawberries can be consumed as a natural antioxidants source. Antioxidants from fruits and vegetables protect humans from oxidative stress and its deleterious consequence. Strawberry is a beautiful bright berry with excellent visual appearance and delicious flavour is one of the major source of antioxidant, high ascorbic acid and phenolic contents. Phenolic compounds present in strawberries are hydroxycinnamic acids (*p*-cumaric), flavonols (quercetin, kaempferol and myricetin), hydroxybenzoic acids (gallic and ellagic acids), flavan-3-ols (catequins, hydrolysable tannins (epicatechins), (ellagitannins), and anthocyanins, being pelargonidin-3-glycoside, the most chief flavonoid pigment. It is found that strawberry extract increased the activity of antioxidant and oxidative stress repair enzymes. Strawberry flavonoids are also able to chelate metal ions and therefore prevent generation of reactive oxygen species. Flavonoids have been shown to inhibit lipid peroxidation within the phospholipid bilayer by localization within the polar and nonpolar phases. Quercetin has been shown to increase glutathione S-transferase activity, an enzyme responsible for protecting cells against oxidative stress. The World Health Organization signifies the vital role of small colorful fruits for their antioxidant activity of phenolic components that prevents humans from many health problems like diabetes, cancer, cardiovascular diseases and obesity. Three-fold more ellagitannins content are present in berries than walnuts and pecans and about fifteen-fold more than other fruits and nuts. Many biologically significant mechanisms are exhibited by phenolic compounds like detoxification or scavenging of ROS, blocking ROS production, impacting cell cycle, tumors

suppression, modulation of signal transduction, detoxifying enzymes, apoptosis, and metabolism.

Strawberry As Oral Disease Preventive

Oral health has a significant effect on overall health and quality of life. Conditions such as periodontitis, xerostomia, mucositis, and tooth decay are associated with co-morbidities such as decreased saliva production, difficulty in chewing and swallowing, and loss of taste. In addition, new diagnoses of oral cancer are estimated to be in excess of 35,000 in 2010 (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, 2009). Strawberry phytochemicals could improve oral maladies. Fruit phenolics have been shown to elicit significant protective effects on oral mucosa when evaluated in numerous pre-clinical animal models and may be a novel prevention tool instead of costly pharmaceutical agents that may have undesirable side effects. The association of chronic disease and oral health is possibly due to infection, chronic inflammation, genetic predisposition, and potentially nutrition. Reported a dose-dependent anti-proliferative effect in oral cell lines with a phenolic-enriched strawberry extract. Inhibition of proliferation of human oral tumour cell lines with both crude extracts and 32 isolated compounds from strawberries was reported.

Anti-Ageing Property of Strawberry

There are numerous cognitive and motor behavioural deficit that occur during aging and are related to the alteration in the striatal dopamine (DA) system or in the cerebellum. Long term exposure to oxidation and inflammation are thought to be the contributing factors to the decrements in cognitive and motor performance that is evident in aging and other neurodegenerative diseases. Strawberry exerts their effects directly by changing cell signalling to improve or increase neuronal communication, calcium buffering ability neuro-protective stress shock, plasticity and stress signalling pathway. The strawberry consumption show better

protection for spatial deficits the studies that have been initiated by the researcher suggest that phytochemicals present in antioxidant-rich foods such as strawberries may have benefits in retarding functional age-related, cognitive behavioural deficits and central nervous system thus positively impacting neurodegenerative disease in humans also.

Strawberry And Leukemia

Strawberries have known anti-cancer benefits like it inhibit the initiation and promotion of the carcinogenic process. The strawberries and other types of berries have methanol extracts, that helps to inhibit the growth of colon, prostate, breast, and oral cancer cells. The need is to develop alternative dietary and therapeutic approaches that may be more effective for prevention or treatment of this disease, reported that the patients with high-risk of B-lineage suffer apoptotic cell death in cell lines due to resveratrol, curcumin, carnosol, and quercetin including those that carry the translocation of t (4;11) as well as the other lines without the translocation. The bioactive components displaying anti-cancer activities have been shown by strawberries, the purified foam of these constituents induce apoptosis in high-risk t (4;11) cell lines. The quercetin, kaempferol, and ellagic acid are the most effective anti-leukemia phytochemicals. The fresh strawberries (w/w) contains 1.1–1.9 mg and 0.5 mg per 100 g of quercetin and kaempferol respectively. The in-vitro studies confirm that the components of strawberries kill leukemic cells in a cell culture system.

Extraction

Soxhlet Extraction

History:

Soxhlet extraction is an advanced extraction technique that involves repeatedly circulating the same solvent through the extractor. In 1897, Franz Ritter Von Soxhlet, professor of agriculture chemistry at the technical university of Munich,

developed this extraction technique. This is a very technique for separation goals in which the analyte is concentrated from matrix as a whole or separated from specific interfering substances.

Principle

The Soxhlet extraction method uses a small amount of solvent and is very cost-effective. The Soxhlet extraction uses the solvent reflux and siphon principle to continuously extract the solid matter by pure solvent, which saves the solvent extraction efficiency and high efficiency. The solid sample is placed on thimbles shaped filter paper, positioned into Soxhlet extractor and the device is assembled. The solvent is added to the solvent reservoir flask and mounted onto a heating mantle. After, heating the condensed vapours of the solvent come in contact with the sample powder and the soluble part of the powder gets mixed with the solvent for extraction. When the solvent surface exceeds the maximum height of the siphon, the solvent containing the extract is siphon back. The flask is repeated, extracting the portion of the material each time so that the solid material is constantly used as a pure solvent and the extracted material is concentrated in the flask.

Uses

- ✓ The soxhlet extraction process is the most useful technique for soli-liquid extraction in many fields like Agriculture, pharmaceuticals, foodstuffs and also in the environment.
- ✓ Soxhlet apparatus is allow for continuous treatment of a sample with a solvent over a period of hours or days to extract the compound of interest.
- ✓ This technique is useful to determine the lipid and fat contents of animals and plant tissues.
- ✓ It is also used to determine the percent of fat content in a food sample by weight in a sample.

Soxhlet Description

The crude substance is placed in thimble shaped filter paper which is then kept in a glass cylinder. This cylinder is provided with a siphon tube and

an inlet tube. A water condenser is attached to the cylinder at the top. The entire assemble is fitted into the neck of around bottom flask containing the solvent. The solvent flask heated in a water bath or sand bath. The solvent vapours reach the cylinder through the inlet tube and conduce on passing upward into the condenser. The condensed solvent comes in contact with the crude organic substance and dissolves it. As soon as the solution reaches at the top end of the siphon tube. In this way, a continuous supply of solvent vapours is maintained in the cylinder and the dissolved organic compounds flows back into the flask. Finally, the heating is stopped and the solution in the flask is distilled to cover the solvent, while the organic compound is left behind.

Collection Of Strawberry

Strawberry fruit was collected in the nearby market and it was dried at room temperature. The dried strawberries were crushed partially using mortar and pestle it is grinded into a powder. As for the soxhlet extraction process, NaOH is used as solvent because folate is soluble in NaOH solution.

Procedure

1. First weight approximately 20 - 30g of sample dried strawberry powder in the filter paper.
2. Next close the filter paper and keep in siphon tube. Adjust the apparatus.
3. Fit water IN and OUT in condenser must remembered cool water should pass through below to top of the condenser to avid air bubbles.
4. Then, after fill the solvent NaOH and 100ml water added together in 50:50 ratio (40 to 60°C) in siphon tube it would 1st siphon then fill half as well on siphon tube.
5. Start heating on water bath the temperature of water bath should 70-75°C. Run the system till 7 hours for clearance ethanol will clear at siphon tube, it means extraction is completed.

6. Then after remove the sample from siphon tube, recover the ethanol. Keep filter paper sample and flask in drying oven for 3 hours.
7. When the smell of the sample is free from ethanol it means it has been dried. Weigh filter paper and flask.

Then, finally the folate from the strawberry extract was collect in the flask.

Phytochemical Constituent Test

Bratton – Marshall Test

The Bratton- Marshall test is also known as Azo Dye chemical test is a colorimetric method used to detect the presence of certain compounds, particularly Folate (Vitamin B9) and other aromatic amines in the biological samples.

Mechanism

The Bratton- Marshall test is based on the diazotization reaction of sulfanilic acid with nitrous acid which forms a diazonium salt. This salt then couples with the aromatic amines to form a colored azo compound.

Reagents

Sulfanilic acid: A colourless, crystalline solid.

Nitrous acid(NaNO₂): A strong oxidizing agent.

Acetic acid (CH₃COOH) : A weak organic acid.

Procedure

1.Preparation of the sample: The sample should be extracted using Soxhlet apparatus.

2.Addition Of Sulfanilic Acid: A few drops of sulfanilic solution is added to the sample solution

3. Addition of nitrous acid: A few drops of nitrous solution is added to the mixture.

4. Acidification With Acetic Acid: A few drops of acetic acid is added to the mixture.

Observation

➤ Colour Change

The mixture turns pink, indicating the presence of folate.

➤ Intensity Of Colour:

The intensity of the color is proportional to the concentration of the compound.

RESULT

It indicates the presence of pink color. So, Folate is present in the sample.

CONCLUSION

Strawberries are a rich source of folate, making them a valuable natural remedy for preventing and treating anemia. Regular consumption of strawberries can help alleviate anemia symptoms and improve overall health. Folate plays a crucial role in preventing and treating anemia. Strawberries, being an excellent source of folate, can be a vital component of an anemia prevention and treatment plan. A dietary approach to managing anemia, including consumption of folate-rich foods like strawberries can be effective and sustainable way to prevent and treat anemia. This study highlight the importance of fruit consumption particularly strawberries in maintaining healthy levels and preventing anemia. The findings of this study suggest that strawberry based interventions could be a valuable tool in preventing and treating anemia, particularly in populations with limited access to fortified foods or supplements.

REFERENCES

1. Turner J, Parsi M, Badireddy M. Anemia. [Updated from 2023 Aug 8] In :Starpearls [Internet]. Treasure Island (FL) :Starpearls publishing; 2025 jan. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK499994/>.
2. National Center for Biotechnology Information (2025). PubChem Compound Summary for CID 135398658, Folic Acid. Retrieved January 26, 2025 from <https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/compound/Folic-Acid>.
3. PubChem [Internet]. Bethesda (MD): National Library of Medicine (US), National Center for Biotechnology Information; 2004-. PubChem Compound Summary for CID 135398658, Folic Acid; [cited 2025 Jan. 26]. Available from: <https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/compound/Folic-Acid>.
4. Cesar G Victora, Linda Adair, Caroline Fall, Pedro C Hallal, Reynaldo Martorell, Linda Richter, Harshpal Singh Sachdev, Maternal and child undernutrition: consequences for adult health and human capital, *The Lancet*, Volume 371, Issue 9609, 2008, Pages 340-357, ISSN 0140-6736, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(07\)61692-](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(07)61692-) (<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0140673607616924>).
5. Antony AC. Megaloblastic anemias. In: Hoffman R, Benz EJ, Silberstein LE, et al, eds. *Hematology: Basic Principles and Practice*. 8th ed. Philadelphia, PA: Elsevier; 2023:chap 40.
6. Kumar V, Abbas AK, Aster JC. Hematopoietic and lymphoid systems. In: Kumar V, Abbas AK, Aster JC, Deyrup AT, Das A, eds. *Robbins and Kumar Basic Pathology*. 11th ed. Philadelphia, PA: Elsevier; 2023:chap 10.
7. Stabler SP. Megaloblastic anemias. In: Goldman L, Cooney KA, eds. *Goldman-Cecil Medicine*. 27th ed. Philadelphia, PA: Elsevier; 2024:chap 150.
8. The Johns Hopkins University, The Johns Hopkins Hospital and health system. Sterile fluid supply information 2004.
9. Carol DerSarkissian, MD on December 05, 2022. Written by WebMD Editorial Contributors on Folic acid deficiency.
10. Chandler, C.K., E.E. Albrechts, C.M. Howard, and J.K. Brecht. 1997. 'Sweet Charlie' strawberry. *HortScience* 32:1132-1133.
11. Chandler, C.K., D.E. Legard, and C.A. Sims. 1997. 'Rosa Linda' strawberry. *HortScience* 32:1134-1135.
12. Hancock, J.F. 1999. Strawberries. CAB Intl., New York. Sims, C.A., C.K. Chandler, J.S. Eastridge, and R.R. Golaszewski. 1997. Seasonal changes in fruit quality of several

- strawberry genotypes grown in Florida. *Adv. Strawberry Res.* 16:48.
13. R B Smith and L J Skog, University of Guelph, Vineland Station, Ontario, Canada. Elsevier Science limited, Copy right 2004.
 14. Basu, A., Nguyen, A., Betts, N. M., & Lyons, T. J. (2014). Strawberry as a functional food: An evidence-based review. *Critical Reviews in Food Science and Nutrition*, 54(6), 790–806.
 15. Giampieri, F., Forbes-Hernandez, T.Y., Gasparrini, M., Alvarez-Suarez, J. M., Afrin, S., Bompadre, S., ... & Battino, M. (2015). Strawberry as a health promoter: An evidence based review. *Food & function*, 6(5), 1386–1398.
 16. Giampieri, F., Tulipani, S., Alvarez-Suarez, J. M., Quiles, J. L., Mezzetti, B., & Battino, M. (2012). The strawberry: Composition, nutritional quality, and impact on human health. *Nutrition*, 28(1), 9–19.
 17. Sharma, G. I. R. I. S. H., & Thakur, M. S. (2008). Evaluation of different strawberry cultivars for yield and quality characters in Himachal Pradesh. *Agricultural Science Digest*, 28(3), 213–215.
 18. Sharma, R. R. (2002). *Growing Strawberries*. International Book Distributing Company, Charbagh, Lucknow-226004. U.P. (India), pp. 1–33.
 19. Sharma, S., Joshi, V. K., & Abrol, G. (2009). An overview on Strawberry [*Fragaria × ananassa* (Weston) Duchesne ex Rozier] wine production technology, composition, maturation and quality evaluation.
 20. Tulipani, S., Alvarez-Suarez, J. M., Busco, F., Bompadre, S., Quiles, J. L., Mezzetti, B., et al. (2011). Strawberry consumption improves plasma antioxidant status and erythrocyte resistance to oxidative haemolysis in humans. *Food Chemistry*, 128(1), 180–186.
 21. Tulipani, S., Romandini, S., Suarez, J. M. A., Capocasa, F., Mezzetti, B., Battino, M., ... & Novembrino, C. (2008). Folate content in different strawberry genotypes and folate status in healthy subjects after strawberry consumption. *Biofactors*, 34(1), 47–55.
 22. E. Barclay Poling Professor Emeritus, NC State University on Strawberry plant structure and growth habit.
 23. Adom, K. K. and R. H. Liu, 2002. Antioxidant activity of grains. *Journal of agricultural and food chemistry*, 50(21): 6182-6187.
 24. Ames, B. N. and L. S. Gold, 1991. Endogenous mutagens and the causes of aging and cancer. *Mutation Research/Fundamental and Molecular mechanisms of mutagenesis*, 250(1-2): 3-16.
 25. Ames, B. N., M. K. Shigenaga and L. S. Gold, 1993. DNA lesions, inducible DNA repair, and cell division: Three key factors in mutagenesis and carcinogenesis. *Environmental health perspectives*, 101(Suppl 5): 35
 26. Andres-Lacueva, C., B. Shukitt-Hale, R. L. Galli, O. Jauregui, R. M. Lamuela-Raventos and J. A. Joseph, 2005. Anthocyanins in aged blueberry-fed rats are found centrally and may enhance memory. *Nutritional neuroscience*, 8(2): 111-120.
 27. Basu, A., M. Wilkinson, K. Penugonda, B. Simmons, N. M. Betts and T. J. Lyons, 2009. Freeze-dried strawberry powder improves lipid profile and lipid peroxidation in women with metabolic syndrome: Baseline and post intervention effects. *Nutritional Journal*, 8: 43-45.
 28. Battino, M., J. Beekwilder, B. Denoyes-Rothan, M. Laimer, G.J. McDougall and B. Mezzetti, 2009. Bioactive compounds in berries relevant to human health. *Nutrition reviews*, 67: S145-S150.
 29. Bell, D. R. and K. Gochenaur, 2006. Direct vasoactive and vasoprotective properties of

- anthocyanin-rich extracts. *Journal of applied physiology*, 100(4): 1164-1170.
30. Connor, A. M., J. J. Luby, J. F. Hancock, S. Berkheimer and E. J. Hanson, 2002. Changes in fruit antioxidant activity among blueberry cultivars during cold-temperature storage. *Journal of agricultural and food chemistry*, 50(4): 893-898.
31. Cantuti-Castelvetri, I., B. Shukitt-Hale and J. A. Joseph, 2000. Neurobehavioral aspects of antioxidants in aging. *International journal of developmental neuroscience*, 18(4-5): 367-381.
32. Dai, Z., Y. Li, L. Quarles, T. Song, W. Pan, H. Zhou and Z. Xiao, 2007. Resveratrol enhances proliferation and osteoblastic differentiation in human mesenchymal stem cells via er-dependent erk1/2 activation. *Phytomedicine*, 14(12): 806-814.
33. Bagchi, D., C. Sen, M. Bagchi and M. Atalay, 2004. Anti-angiogenic, antioxidant, and anti-carcinogenic properties of a novel anthocyanin-rich berry extract formula. *Biochemistry (Moscow)*, 69(1): 75-80.
34. Eberhardt, M. V., C. Y. Lee and R. H. Liu, 2000. Nutrition: Antioxidant activity of fresh apples. *Nature*, 405(6789): 903-904.
35. Dörrie, J., H. Gerauer, Y. Wachter and S. J. Zunino, 2001. Resveratrol induces extensive apoptosis by depolarizing mitochondrial membranes and activating caspase-9 in acute lymphoblastic leukemia cells. *Cancer research*, 61(12): 4731
36. Rice-evans, C. A., N. J. Miller, P. G. Bolwell, P. M. Bramley and J. B. Pridham, 1995. The relative antioxidant activities of plant-derived polyphenolic flavonoids. *Free radical research*, 22(4): 375-383.
37. Joseph, J. A., B. Shukitt-Hale, N. A. Denisova, D. Bielinski, A. Martin, J. J. McEwen and P. C. Bickford, 1999. Reversals of age-related declines in neuronal signal transduction, cognitive, and motor behavioral deficits with blueberry, spinach, or strawberry dietary supplementation. *The Journal of neuroscience*, 19(18): 8114-812.
38. Tsuda, T., 2008. Regulation of adipocyte function by anthocyanins; possibility of preventing the metabolic syndrome. *Journal of agricultural and food chemistry*, 56(3): 642-646.
39. Häkkinen, S. H., S. O. Kärenlampi, I. M. Heinonen, H. M. Mykkänen and A. R. Törrönen, 1999. Content of the flavonols quercetin, myricetin, and kaempferol in 25 edible berries. *Journal of agricultural and food chemistry*, 47(6): 2274-2279.
40. Häkkinen, S. H. and A. R. Törrönen, 2000. Content of flavonols and selected phenolic acids in strawberries and vaccinium species: Influence of cultivar, cultivation site and technique. *Food research international*, 33(6): 517-524.
41. Hakala, M., A. Lapveteläinen, R. Huopalahti, H. Kallio and R. Tahvonen, 2003. Effects of varieties and cultivation conditions on the composition of strawberries. *Journal of food Composition and Analysis*, 16(1): 67-80.
42. Zhao, Z. and M. H. Moghadasian, 2008. Chemistry, natural sources, dietary intake and pharmacokinetic properties of ferulic acid: A review. *Food Chemistry*, 109(4): 691-702.
43. Wang, H., G. Cao and L. Ronald, 1996. Total antioxidant capacity of fruits. *Journal of agricultural and food chemistry*, 44(3): 701-705
44. Sellappan, S., C. C. Akoh and G. Krewer, 2002. Phenolic compounds and antioxidant capacity of georgia-grown blueberries and blackberries. *Journal of agricultural and food chemistry*, 50(8): 2432-2438
45. Carkeet, C., B. A. Clevidence and J. A. Novotny, 2008. Anthocyanin excretion by

- humans increases linearly with increasing strawberry dose. *The Journal of nutrition*, 138(5): 897.
46. Khanizadeh, S., R. Tsao, D. Rekika, R. Yang, M. T. Charles and H. Vasantha Rupasinghe, 2008. Polyphenol composition and total antioxidant capacity of selected apple genotypes for processing. *Journal of food composition and analysis*, 21(5): 396-401.
47. Nickel, T., D. Schmauss, H. Hanssen, Z. Sicic, B. Krebs, S. Jankl, C. Summo, P. Fraunberger, A. K. Walli and S. Pfeiler, 2009. Oxldl uptake by dendritic cells induces upregulation of scavenger-receptors, maturation and differentiation. *Atherosclerosis*, 205(2): 442-450.
48. Mazur, W., M. Uehara, K. Wahala and H. Adlercreutz, 2000. Phyto-oestrogen content of berries, and plasma concentrations and urinary excretion of enterolactone after a single strawberry-meal in human subjects. *British journal of nutrition*, 83(4): 381-387.
49. Seeram, N. P., R. Lee, H. S. Scheuller and D. Heber, 2006. Identification of phenolic compounds in strawberries by liquid chromatography electrospray ionization mass spectroscopy. *Food chemistry*, 97(1): 1-11.
50. Sellappan, S., C. C. Akoh and G. Krewer, 2002. Phenolic compounds and antioxidant capacity of georgia-grown blueberries and blackberries. *Journal of agricultural and food chemistry*, 50(8): 2432-2438.
51. Heo, H. J. and C. Y. Lee, 2005. Strawberry and its anthocyanins reduce oxidative stress-induced apoptosis in pc12 cells. *Journal of agricultural and food chemistry*, 53(6): 1984-1989.
52. Meyskens Jr, F. L. and E. Szabo, 2005. Diet and cancer: The disconnect between epidemiology and randomized clinical trials. *Cancer epidemiology biomarkers & prevention*, 14(6): 1366-1369.
53. Ramos, S., M. Alía, L. Bravo and L. Goya, 2005. Comparative effects of food-derived polyphenols on the viability and apoptosis of a human hepatoma cell line (hepg2). *Journal of agricultural and food chemistry*, 53(4): 1271-1280.
54. Lotito, S. B. and B. Frei, 2004. The increase in human plasma antioxidant capacity after apple consumption is due to the metabolic effect of fructose on urate, not apple-derived antioxidant flavonoids. *Free radical biology and medicine*, 37(2): 251-258.
55. Zhang, Y., N. P. Seeram, R. Lee, L. Feng and D. Heber, 2008. Isolation and identification of strawberry phenolics with antioxidant and human cancer cell antiproliferative properties. *Journal of agricultural and food chemistry*, 56(3): 670-675.
56. Eberhardt, M. V., C. Y. Lee and R. H. Liu, 2000. Nutrition: Antioxidant activity of fresh apples. *Nature*, 405(6789): 903-904.
57. Movileanu, L., I. Neagoe and M. L. Flonta, 2000. Interaction of the antioxidant flavonoid quercetin with planar lipid bilayers. *International journal of pharmaceuticals*, 205(1-2): 135-146.
58. Stapleton, P. A., M. E. James, A. G. Goodwill and J. C. Frisbee, 2008. Obesity and vascular dysfunction. *Pathophysiology*, 15(2): 79-89.
59. Shukitt-Hale, B., F. C. Lau and J. A. Joseph, 2008. Berry fruit supplementation and the aging brain. *Journal of agricultural and food chemistry*, 56(3): 636-641.
60. Ritchie, C. S., K. Joshipura, H. C. Hung and C. W. Douglass, 2002. Nutrition as a mediator in the relation between oral and systemic disease: Associations between specific measures of adult oral health and nutrition outcomes. *Critical reviews in oral biology & medicine*, 13(3): 291-300.

61. Zunino, S. J., D. H. Storms, Y. Zhang and N. P. Seeram, 2009. Growth arrest and induction of apoptosis in high-risk leukemia cells by strawberry components in vitro. *Journal of functional foods*, 1(2): 153-160.
62. Samia, I., Abbasi, U.A., Khalid, N. (2019). Strawberry (*Fragaria ananassa* Duch): phytochemicals, nutraceuticals and health benefits. A brief Review. *World Journal of Biology and Biotechnology*, 4(3), 25-34. Issue:3, Volume: 4. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.33865/wjb.004.03.0236>.
63. P. Shivranjani, S. Maithreyee, D. M. Nivedha., A comparative bioavailability study of folic acid present in spinachia oleracea using Soxhlet extraction, chemical methods and chromatographic and spectroscopic studies. *International Journal of Research Publication and Reviews*, Vol 3, Issue 6, pp 2323-2333, June 2022.
64. Ghulam Hussain, Ghulam, Title on extraction , principal and working and usage of soxhlet, 07 july 2023. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/372658021_Soxhlet_Extraction_principal_working_Usage..

HOW TO CITE: Mounika K.*, K. B. Ilango, Ajith M. S., Babu S., Kalpana D., Nishanth Kannan B., Ramya R., Selvakumar R., 'Folate from Strawberries' A Sustainable Solution for Anemia, Prevention and Treatment, *Int. J. of Pharm. Sci.*, 2025, Vol 3, Issue 2, 1026-1047. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14870157>